

Absolute Accuracy Assessment of Maxar's Worldwide 3D Textured Mesh

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Table 1.0.1: Summary of Results

Type of Points	LUB (m) [†]			Mean Δ (m) [‡]			BE (m) [§]		
	LE90	CE90	SE90	East	North	Up	LE90	CE90	SE90
APEBC ^{††}	1.80	1.40	2.15	0.09	0.00	-0.53	1.76	1.37	2.11
Ground	1.68	1.42	2.00	0.10	0.01	-0.40	1.59	1.37	1.94

[†] Least upper bound at confidence level 90%, see [section 2.4](#)

[‡] The signed mean, where Δ is computed by subtracting the reference product from the evaluated product. An “up” value of -0.53 indicates the MAXAR product is 0.53 m below the reference product.

[§] Best estimate; see [section 2.4](#) for additional information about the difference between BE and LUB.

^{††} All points except building corners; see [section 3](#) for additional details.

1. Introduction

Under contract to Maxar, the Photogrammetry Team within the Center for Advanced Spatial Technologies (CAST) at the University of Arkansas (UofA) conducted an independent assessment of the absolute accuracy of the 3D textured mesh product over 25 sites spanning three continents. The spherical error at the 0.9 probability level (SE90) for the products tested is well under 3 meters, and not much more than 2 meters, with specific values provided in [table 1.0.1](#) for All Points Except Building Corners (APEBC) and Ground points. The LE90, CE90, and SE90 scalar accuracy metrics, which correspond to vertical, horizontal, and 3D radial, respectively, are provided for both Least Upper Bound (LUB) and Best Estimate (BE). Finally, the overall signed mean, or bias, is provided in the East, North, and Up directions; notice essentially zero horizontal bias, but roughly a half-meter negative vertical bias.

[Section 2](#) discusses the accuracy assessment methodologies, [section 3](#) summarizes the results, [section 4](#) through [section 6](#) summarize special considerations impacting the analysis, and [section 7](#) provides summary and conclusions.

2. Methodology

Assessing the absolute accuracy of a product requires a reference product with accuracy generally five times better than that to be analyzed¹. For example, if we think that the product to be analyzed could be as good as 2 meters SE90, then we would need a reference product with accuracy at least as good as 0.4 meters SE90.

We have used three basic types of reference products, some of which have possible sub-cases within them. Broadly speaking, these reference products fall within the following three categories, which are addressed in the next three subsections. [Section 2.1](#) addresses the case where the reference product is

¹As presented in section 5.7 of NGA.SIG.0026.05_1.1_ACCSPEC, *Accuracy and Predicted Accuracy in the NSG: Specification and Validation*, also known as Technical Guidance Document 2c (TGD 2c)

Figure 2.1.1: Vricon Explorer tool used to measure 3D coordinates from textured mesh product, with satellite on left and airborne on right

itself also a 3D textured mesh; [section 2.2](#) addresses the case where the reference product is triangulated overlapping images; and [section 2.3](#) address the case where the reference product is a high resolution point cloud. This section concludes with [section 2.4](#), which addresses the absolute accuracy assessment methodology that is applied once measurements are available from the reference and Maxar products.

2.1. Reference Product is a 3D Textured Mesh

We have access to, and have used, only one 3D textured mesh reference product; it is the airborne-derived MIDAS product provided to us by Maxar. Absolute accuracy from this product had been claimed to be on the order of 0.1 to 0.3 meters LE90/CE90/SE90; our analysis has corroborated these numbers, as shown in [section 5](#). The Vricon Explorer, version 3.10.0 (or version 3.9 for some data) “Pro Edition” was used to measure corresponding 3D points that appeared unambiguously on both the Satellite and Airborne products. See [fig. 2.1.1](#) for a screenshot of Vricon Explorer over the Las Vegas dataset, where Maxar’s satellite-derived 3D textured mesh is on the left and the Midas airborne-derived 3D textured mesh is on the right.

2.2. Reference Product is Triangulated Overlapping Images

In this subsection, we discuss three cases where we used triangulated overlapping images as the reference product. First, we had GPS survey controlled aerial frame images; second, we had GPS survey-controlled Worldview satellite images; and third, we had Worldview (WV) satellite images that were planned to be controlled to ICESAT-2 data.

Figure 2.2.1: SOCET GXP tool was used to triangulate aerial photographs and measure 3D points of interest

2.2.1. Controlled Aerial Frame Images

Through connections that CAST has made with the Arkansas Department of Transportation (ARDOT) and municipalities such as Bentonville, AR and Ardmore, OK, we obtained blocks of aerial frame images acquired from calibrated digital cameras from a sample of eight sites. We also had surveyed ground control points for each of these sites and used these as additional measurements in the block triangulation. See [fig. 2.2.1](#) for a screenshot of image chips of aerial frame photographs centered on a 3D point of interest in Bentonville, AR; these photographs were triangulated using SOCET GXP. The corresponding point is also shown in Vricon Explorer.

2.2.2. Controlled Worldview Satellite Images

For one of the sites, Fort Bragg, we had a block of overlapping WV satellite images that were not used to build the Maxar 3D textured mesh product, and we triangulated them using a plentiful number of GPS surveyed ground control points (GCPs).

2.2.3. Worldview Satellite Images Vertically Controlled by ICESAT-2

For our site in northwest Canada, shown in [fig. 2.2.2](#), we had a WV stereopair that was not used to build the Maxar 3D textured mesh product, and although we did not have GCPs, our plan was to obtain and leverage ICESAT-2 data to vertically control our stereopair. Results could not be completed in time to include in this version of the report.

Figure 2.2.2: Maxar assessment site, located in the Richardson Mountains, on the western bound of the Mackenzie Delta in the Northwest Territories, Canada

2.3. Reference Product is a Point Cloud

The USGS has contracted with local surveying and mapping companies to map much of the US with high resolution aerial lidar collections. Some of them have been validated using terrestrial lidar controlled to GPS surveyed targets. We have used three such sites, which are publicly available from the USGS², as a reference to assess Maxar’s 3D textured mesh product. See fig. 2.3.1 for an example, over northern Colorado, of measuring corresponding 3D points from a point-cloud in CloudCompare and a 3D mesh in Vricon Explorer. Our fourth point-cloud reference product was a UAV lidar collection at low altitude over the Montpelier, VA site.

2.4. Methodology for All Reference Types

To characterize our results, we follow the recommendations³ of the NGA, which includes more detailed descriptions of the terms we summarize here:

- The error components ϵ_x , ϵ_y , and ϵ_z correspond to a local tangent plane coordinate system, East–North–Up (ENU).
- The vertical error $\epsilon_v \equiv |\epsilon_z|$, the horizontal error $\epsilon_h \equiv \sqrt{\epsilon_x^2 + \epsilon_y^2}$, and the spherical error $\epsilon_s \equiv \sqrt{\epsilon_x^2 + \epsilon_y^2 + \epsilon_z^2}$ are always positive.
- The value $\epsilon_{h,XX}$ is the XX percentile of the random variable ϵ_h ; i.e., $prob(\epsilon_h \leq \epsilon_{h90}) = 0.90$.
- LE90 is defined identical to $\epsilon_{v,90}$, CE90 is defined identical to $\epsilon_{h,90}$, and SE90 is identical to $\epsilon_{s,90}$.

² Available from the ScienceBase service of the USGS, <https://www.sciencebase.gov/catalog/>

Figure 2.3.1: CloudCompare tool was used to measure 3D points of interest from lidar point cloud reference data

- The least-upper-bound (lub) is a probabilistic value derived from the errors ϵ . For example, $lub_{\epsilon_{h90}}$ is defined such that

$$prob(\epsilon_{h90} < lub_{\epsilon_{h90}}) \geq 0.90.$$

I.e., it is 90% likely that the true value of CE90 is less than $lub_{\epsilon_{h90}}$. For all lub values discussed in this report, the confidence level is 90%.

- In contrast to the lub, the best estimate (be) values for these metrics are simply order statistics on the observed errors; i.e., $be_{\epsilon_{h90}}$ is the 90th percentile value of ϵ_h .

The SE90 value can be related to the CE90 and LE90 values. Maxar claims an SE90 of 3 m, which is a per-axis sigma value of $3/2.5 = 1.2$ m. Therefore, an SE90 of 3 m corresponds to:

$$CE90 = 2.146 \times 1.2 = 2.575 \text{ m}$$

$$LE90 = 1.645 \times 1.2 = 1.974 \text{ m}$$

The nominal expected relationship between SE90, CE90, and LE90 (scalar accuracy metrics), provided in this report simply to give the reader an intuitive feel for relative magnitudes of these values that occur in practice, assumes a Gaussian distribution of errors. However, the computation of these scalar accuracy metrics does not assume any particular type of distribution or presence/absence of a bias; this claim is consistent with the statement that order statistics are used to compute the values of the scalar accuracy metrics.

³As presented in NGA.SIG.0026.01_1.2_ACCOVER, *Accuracy and Predicted Accuracy in the NSG: Overview and Methodologies*, and related documents.

3. Results

This section summarizes the absolute accuracy results of Maxar’s 3D textured mesh product, accounting for results across all sites. The categories referenced in this section correspond to well-defined points on: the ground, building sides, building roofs, building corners, and building centers. Analysts used a procedure to intersect the diagonals of building corners (of rectangular-footprint buildings) to identify the center, at which location the precise building center was measured. Note, that it is a well-known fact that building corners are challenging to represent precisely in a 3D textured mesh product; and even if they could be represented precisely, current mensuration tools have not yet matured to the state where they can precisely extract building corner locations. Therefore, the purpose of measuring building corners in this analysis was solely to locate and measure the building centers; i.e., the errors in the building corners were not of particular interest, for practical reasons. Thus, the category “All points except building corners” is likely more relevant to most users than the category “All points.” As expected, the magnitude of the former errors are significantly less than that of the latter errors, when a significant number of buildings were measured. The results discussed in the bullets below refer to “All points except building corners” unless specified otherwise.

- [Table 3.0.1](#) shows a summary of the scalar accuracy metrics (LE90, CE90, and SE90) along with the signed mean (aka bias) for each site where measurements were made. SE90 (LUB) values range from around 1.2 to 3.3 meters; typically the sites with larger SE90 also have larger biases, as shown by larger magnitudes in the Signed Mean columns.
- [Table 3.0.2](#) compares the LUB and BE values at each site.
- [Table 3.0.3](#) shows RMSE, Signed Mean, and Standard Deviation, in the East, North, and Up directions, organized by category and aggregated across all sites. Note how close the horizontal components of Signed Mean are to zero, while we observe roughly a half meter of negative vertical bias. One possible explanation for the negative vertical bias is that some portion of the measured points protruded vertically upward from the nominal ground surface, and the reference product tended to model this more precisely than the Maxar product; seldom, if ever, were the points located below the nominal ground surface. Of course, the other possible explanation is that the global errors of the Worldview constellation have a negative vertical bias; this idea could be corroborated or contradicted by comparing a large sample of Multi Image Geopositioning (MIG) solutions, where points are measured directly off of the Worldview overlapping images, to surveyed GCPs. Also, note the standard deviations in the horizontal direction are 0.64 meters, versus 0.98 meters in the vertical direction. The former is largely a function of the strong internal relative geometry of Worldview imagery, while the latter is largely a function of the depth reconstruction via dense matching and correlation of pixel intensity values.
- [Table 3.0.4](#) shows scalar accuracy metrics of RMS error, Mean error, and LE90, CE90, and SE90, organized by category and aggregated across all sites. The best estimate for SE90 is 2.11 meters (LUB of 2.15), and the best estimate of LE90 and CE90 values are 1.76 and 1.37 meters (LUB of 1.80 and 1.40), respectively.

Figure 3.0.1: Scatter of errors horizontally and vertically, for the aggregated point data

- [Table 3.0.5](#) and [table 3.0.6](#) show the variation across 20 Monte Carlo trials due to the randomized selection of a common number of five ground points from each site, which were used to aggregate the data across sites. The value of five was chosen to correspond to the minimum number of ground points across all sites. We have confidence in the stability of the results as a function of number of points used per site due to: the fact that the mean results (second from bottom rows of these tables) across these 20 trials matches closely to the Ground results from [table 3.0.3](#) and [table 3.0.4](#), respectively, and the fact that the standard deviations (bottom rows of these tables) have small values.
- [Figure 3.0.1](#) shows the scatter of errors horizontally and vertically, for the aggregated point data; dots are color-coded by type. Order statistics had been used to compute CE90 and LE90 values of approximately 1.5 m and 2.0 m, respectively.
- [Figure 3.0.2](#) shows the scatter of the per-site global errors (biases), horizontally and vertically, centered at the origin; [Figure 3.0.3](#) shows the same data plotted as quivers at the site locations.

Figure 3.0.2: Scatter of the per-site global errors (biases), horizontally and vertically, centered at the origin

Figure 3.0.3: Scatter of the per-site global errors (biases), horizontally and vertically, plotted at site locations

Table 3.0.1: Summary results from all sites

Site	LUB (m) [†]			Mean Δ (m) [‡]			Reference	Section
	LE90	CE90	SE90	East	North	Up		
Linkoping, Sweden	2.24	1.94	2.83	0.74	0.86	-1.16	Mesh	A.1
Kalmar, Sweden	2.02	1.16	2.23	0.18	0.07	-1.27	Mesh	A.2
Miami, USA	1.57	1.66	2.07	0.07	-1.03	-0.24	Mesh	A.3
San Antonio, USA	1.44	1.30	1.78	0.87	-0.17	-0.13	Mesh	A.4
Chicago, USA	1.36	1.18	1.56	-0.01	-0.30	0.44	Mesh	A.5
New York, USA	1.95	1.73	2.33	-0.52	-0.44	-0.41	Mesh	A.6
Orlando, USA	1.16	1.17	1.42	-0.23	-0.26	-0.35	Mesh	A.7
Weymouth, GBR	1.16	0.86	1.41	0.05	-0.06	0.57	Mesh	A.8
Las Vegas, USA	1.64	0.84	1.76	0.34	0.08	-0.89	Mesh	A.9
Hoover Dam, USA	2.13	1.03	2.24	0.23	0.25	-0.97	Mesh	A.10
Lolldaiga, Kenya	2.65	2.21	3.00	-0.81	0.31	-1.17	Mesh	A.11
Ol Maisor, Kenya	2.32	1.88	2.73	0.00	0.31	0.20	Mesh	A.12
Fayetteville, AR, USA	2.79	0.88	2.89	0.17	0.27	-1.74	Aerial	A.13
Bentonville, AR, USA	1.87	1.00	1.94	0.44	0.17	-1.01	Aerial	A.14
Ardmore, OK, USA	2.91	2.09	3.29	-1.03	0.79	-1.44	Aerial	A.15
Little Rock, AR, USA	1.68	1.03	1.81	-0.06	0.29	-0.81	Aerial	A.16
Hamburg, AR, USA	2.39	1.70	2.83	0.25	0.61	0.19	Aerial	A.17
Jonesboro, AR, USA	0.68	1.15	1.21	-0.15	-0.65	0.11	Aerial	A.18
Texarkana, AR, USA	2.87	0.80	2.98	-0.11	0.00	-1.37	Aerial	A.19
Benton, AR, USA	1.13	1.03	1.32	0.05	-0.28	-0.03	Aerial	A.20
Fort Bragg, USA	1.01	2.15	2.29	0.91	0.14	0.18	Satellite	A.21
Montpelier, VA, USA	-	-	-	-0.31	-0.18	-1.93	UAV lidar	A.22
Northeastern Illinois, USA	-	-	-	-1.28	-0.57	1.28	Ground lidar	A.23
Longmont, CO, USA	-	-	-	-0.21	-0.09	-0.33	Ground lidar	A.24
Harper's Ferry, WV, USA	-	-	-	-0.04	0.31	-1.27	Ground lidar	A.25

[†] Least upper bound at confidence level 90%, see [section 2.4](#)

[‡] The signed mean, where Δ is computed by subtracting the reference product from the evaluated product. This means that, e.g., an “up” value of 1 indicates the MAXAR product is 1 m above the reference product.

Table 3.0.2: Comparison of LUB and BE Statistics for All Sites

Site	LUB (m)			BE (m)		
	LE90	CE90	SE90	LE90	CE90	SE90
Linkoping, Sweden	2.24	1.94	2.83	1.88	1.85	2.44
Kalmar, Sweden	2.02	1.16	2.23	1.89	1.06	2.13
Miami, USA	1.57	1.66	2.07	1.33	1.54	1.85
San Antonio, USA	1.44	1.30	1.78	1.16	1.26	1.62
Chicago, USA	1.36	1.18	1.56	1.05	1.10	1.37
New York, USA	1.95	1.73	2.33	1.58	1.48	2.11
Orlando, USA	1.16	1.17	1.42	1.04	1.01	1.32
Weymouth, GBR	1.16	0.86	1.41	1.07	0.76	1.16
Las Vegas, USA	1.64	0.84	1.76	1.53	0.79	1.60
Hoover Dam, USA	2.13	1.03	2.24	1.69	0.90	1.82
Lolldaiga, Kenya	2.65	2.21	3.00	2.18	1.72	2.68
Ol Maisor, Kenya	2.32	1.88	2.73	1.87	1.55	2.12
Fayetteville, AR, USA	2.79	0.88	2.89	2.41	0.80	2.61
Bentonville, AR, USA	1.87	1.00	1.94	1.69	0.97	1.79
Ardmore, OK, USA	2.91	2.09	3.29	2.30	1.73	2.93
Little Rock, AR, USA	1.68	1.03	1.81	1.45	0.80	1.59
Hamburg, AR, USA	2.39	1.70	2.83	1.92	1.26	2.25
Jonesboro, AR, USA	0.68	1.15	1.21	0.57	1.07	1.15
Texarkana, AR, USA	2.87	0.80	2.98	2.19	0.72	2.31
Benton, AR, USA	1.13	1.03	1.32	1.02	0.85	1.19
Fort Bragg, USA	1.01	2.15	2.29	0.75	1.72	1.90
Montpelier, VA, USA	-	-	-	-	-	-
Northeastern Illinois, USA	-	-	-	-	-	-
Longmont, CO, USA	-	-	-	-	-	-
Harper's Ferry, WV, USA	-	-	-	-	-	-

Note: Statistics are omitted for sites where there are too few samples for reliable calculation.

Table 3.0.3: Aggregated ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.69	0.67	1.21
Signed Mean	0.11	0.01	-0.63
Standard dev	0.69	0.67	1.04
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.65	0.64	1.12
Signed Mean	0.09	0.00	-0.53
Standard dev	0.64	0.64	0.98
Ground			
RMSE	0.64	0.63	0.99
Signed Mean	0.10	0.01	-0.40
Standard dev	0.64	0.63	0.90
Building Sides			
RMSE	0.70	0.78	1.07
Signed Mean	0.10	-0.14	-0.23
Standard dev	0.69	0.77	1.05
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.62	0.58	1.24
Signed Mean	0.05	0.06	-0.78
Standard dev	0.62	0.58	0.97
Building Corners			
RMSE	0.88	0.79	1.60
Signed Mean	0.20	0.02	-1.08
Standard dev	0.85	0.79	1.18
Building Centers			
RMSE	0.75	0.66	1.32
Signed Mean	0.26	-0.03	-0.71
Standard dev	0.71	0.66	1.12

Table 3.0.4: Aggregated error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.21	0.96	1.55
Mean	0.97	0.82	1.38
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.94	1.47	2.27
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.98	1.52	2.33
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.12	0.91	1.44
Mean	0.90	0.78	1.29
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.76	1.37	2.11
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.80	1.40	2.15
Ground			
RMS	0.99	0.90	1.34
Mean	0.80	0.78	1.22
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.59	1.37	1.94
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.68	1.42	2.00
Building Sides			
RMS	1.07	1.05	1.50
Mean	0.88	0.92	1.36
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.65	1.61	2.19
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.73	1.75	2.35
Building Roofs			
RMS	1.24	0.85	1.50
Mean	1.00	0.73	1.34
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.88	1.25	2.17
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.95	1.31	2.23
Building Corners			
RMS	1.60	1.18	1.99
Mean	1.31	1.02	1.80
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.60	1.83	2.88
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.68	1.91	3.01
Building Centers			
RMS	1.32	1.00	1.66
Mean	1.05	0.85	1.47
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.92	1.53	2.37
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.13	1.99	2.54

Table 3.0.5: Aggregated ENU error via random selection of five errors from each site

Trial	East			North			Up		
	RMSE	Mean	SD	RMSE	Mean	SD	RMSE	Mean	SD
1	0.68	-0.01	0.68	0.62	0.01	0.62	1.10	-0.39	1.04
2	0.61	0.01	0.61	0.61	0.04	0.61	1.10	-0.42	1.02
3	0.65	0.00	0.65	0.59	-0.04	0.59	1.05	-0.40	0.98
4	0.66	-0.05	0.66	0.62	0.00	0.62	1.07	-0.43	0.98
5	0.64	0.02	0.64	0.66	0.01	0.66	1.08	-0.45	0.99
6	0.73	-0.03	0.73	0.66	0.05	0.66	1.08	-0.46	0.98
7	0.61	-0.03	0.61	0.62	-0.02	0.62	1.13	-0.40	1.06
8	0.65	-0.05	0.65	0.63	0.01	0.64	1.11	-0.40	1.04
9	0.76	0.00	0.77	0.62	-0.01	0.62	1.13	-0.41	1.06
10	0.67	-0.03	0.68	0.60	-0.01	0.60	1.18	-0.44	1.09
11	0.63	-0.01	0.63	0.69	0.02	0.69	1.08	-0.40	1.00
12	0.65	0.00	0.66	0.65	0.01	0.65	1.13	-0.37	1.07
13	0.65	-0.03	0.65	0.67	0.02	0.67	1.18	-0.37	1.13
14	0.62	0.00	0.62	0.60	-0.01	0.60	1.01	-0.36	0.95
15	0.71	0.00	0.71	0.60	0.01	0.60	1.05	-0.36	0.99
16	0.67	-0.01	0.67	0.61	-0.01	0.62	1.08	-0.43	1.00
17	0.63	-0.01	0.63	0.62	-0.02	0.62	1.05	-0.38	0.98
18	0.63	0.05	0.63	0.66	-0.01	0.67	1.04	-0.30	1.00
19	0.60	0.02	0.60	0.67	0.05	0.67	1.15	-0.47	1.06
20	0.63	0.03	0.64	0.62	-0.01	0.63	1.09	-0.43	1.01
mean	0.65	-0.01	0.66	0.63	0.01	0.63	1.10	-0.40	1.02
std. dev.	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.04	0.05

Table 3.0.6: Aggregated order statistics via random selection of five errors from each site

Trial	Vertical				Radial Horizontal				3D Spherical			
	RMS	Mean	LE90 BE	LE90 LUB	RMS	Mean	CE90 BE	CE90 LUB	RMS	Mean	SE90 BE	SE90 LUB
1	1.10	0.91	1.80	2.08	0.92	0.79	1.41	1.55	1.43	1.29	2.24	2.37
2	1.10	0.91	1.75	2.12	0.86	0.74	1.34	1.53	1.40	1.26	2.20	2.47
3	1.05	0.87	1.79	1.96	0.88	0.76	1.35	1.48	1.37	1.26	2.03	2.25
4	1.07	0.88	1.81	2.05	0.91	0.79	1.46	1.56	1.40	1.28	2.20	2.37
5	1.08	0.88	1.84	1.99	0.92	0.79	1.31	1.55	1.42	1.29	2.23	2.37
6	1.08	0.86	1.86	1.98	0.98	0.82	1.55	1.72	1.46	1.30	2.32	2.47
7	1.13	0.93	1.98	2.12	0.87	0.75	1.36	1.48	1.42	1.30	2.24	2.37
8	1.11	0.91	1.88	2.13	0.91	0.78	1.48	1.67	1.44	1.30	2.24	2.37
9	1.13	0.96	1.89	2.17	0.98	0.83	1.57	1.80	1.50	1.36	2.26	2.53
10	1.18	0.95	1.98	2.17	0.90	0.78	1.37	1.55	1.48	1.33	2.27	2.58
11	1.08	0.87	1.84	1.99	0.93	0.81	1.41	1.56	1.42	1.30	2.22	2.36
12	1.13	0.91	1.90	2.12	0.92	0.79	1.29	1.48	1.46	1.31	2.29	2.47
13	1.18	0.99	1.96	2.12	0.93	0.79	1.41	1.55	1.51	1.37	2.25	2.47
14	1.01	0.85	1.66	1.85	0.86	0.74	1.41	1.53	1.33	1.22	1.92	2.19
15	1.05	0.85	1.81	1.99	0.93	0.79	1.49	1.67	1.40	1.27	2.20	2.40
16	1.08	0.88	1.79	1.98	0.91	0.79	1.41	1.56	1.41	1.29	2.21	2.27
17	1.05	0.87	1.71	1.99	0.88	0.77	1.41	1.51	1.37	1.25	2.05	2.37
18	1.04	0.84	1.79	1.98	0.92	0.78	1.39	1.53	1.39	1.26	2.21	2.41
19	1.15	0.98	1.88	2.08	0.90	0.77	1.50	1.67	1.46	1.33	2.24	2.44
20	1.09	0.88	1.87	2.12	0.89	0.78	1.38	1.53	1.41	1.27	2.23	2.37
mean	1.10	0.90	1.84	2.05	0.91	0.78	1.41	1.57	1.42	1.29	2.20	2.40
std. dev.	0.05	0.04	0.08	0.09	0.03	0.02	0.07	0.09	0.04	0.04	0.09	0.09

4. Quality Control (QC)

We performed QC on each site by computing standardized errors in the east, north, and up directions as well as standardized 3D radial error. Then, we sorted from largest to smallest by the latter value. Thus, the point with the largest standardized 3D radial error was checked first, and then continued with the point with the next-smallest, and so-on. Each dataset generally contained some outliers, which corresponded to points with standardized errors significantly larger than the remainder of the points. Outliers fell into these three categories: 1) the point was determined to have been measured incorrectly the first time, and then a correction was made, as part of the QC process, to the measurement in the Maxar 3D Tiles product, the reference product, or both; 2) the point was determined to have been a poorly selected point in that it could not be reasonably precisely identified in each product, so a new point was selected and measured; and 3) the Maxar 3D Tiles product was determined to have imprecisely extracted the feature being measured, e.g., by poorly estimating the depth from the sensor to the scene, or height of the feature.

We proceed by showing three examples of category 3; i.e., where the Maxar 3D tiles product imprecisely extracted the feature being measured. The first example was in the Fayetteville site, as shown in [fig. 4.0.1](#), and included a ground point feature of a meter or two in width and of 2 to 3 meters tall, but the entire part of it extending vertically from the ground was chopped off in the Maxar product. One could argue that this point has been categorized as a ground point when it is actually a point that is slightly elevated from the ground. We have followed the convention that a ground point can be anything less than approximately one story, or roughly 3 meters, in height. The statistics reported in the tables of this report could have been even better (smaller errors) if ground points had been restricted such that they could not protrude upward at all from the bare-earth surface. The second and third examples were in the Ardmore site, as shown in [fig. 4.0.2](#) and [fig. 4.0.3](#), and included the top surface of a water tower (base of its antenna) and building dome, respectively, where the tops of the features were chopped off, as in the case of the ground point. It would not be unreasonable for a user who is performing precise mensuration from the Maxar 3D Tiles product to recognize these kinds of occasional artifacts that occur in the product, and to proceed with caution or to avoid making measurements on these features altogether. The level of detail of 3D structures/features in the 3D Textured Mesh product is known to be coarser than anything that would be used as a reference. Therefore, it could be justified for features such as these to be removed from the analysis; it is clearly understood that the error does not exist in the triangulated spaceborne images, but occurs only during dense matching, or object reconstruction, due to limitations in the level of detail that can be achieved.

5. Absolute Accuracy of Reference Datasets

As mentioned in [section 2](#), a good rule of thumb is for the reference to be at least 5 times more accurate than the data that is being evaluated; e.g., if a data provider claims 2 meter SE90, then the reference should be 0.4 meters SE90 or better. The remainder of this paragraph provides evidence that the Midas data has an absolute accuracy likely less than 0.3 meters SE90. Over our Miami site, we had not only Midas airborne derived 3D textured mesh, but also 17 GPS surveyed ground control points (GCPs). We measured each of the 17 points in the Midas data as well as Maxar's satellite-derived 3D mesh and

Figure 4.0.1: Example of a ground point with a large negative height error (2.8 meters). This narrow feature protruding upward from the bare Earth surface could not be represented precisely in 3D, due to the resolution of the source satellite imagery.

computed best estimates for LE90, CE90, and SE90 of 0.11, 0.27, and 0.28 meters, respectively, for the Midas absolute accuracy, as shown in [fig. 5.0.1](#). Note also the reported RMSE, signed mean, and standard deviations in each axis. Signed mean and standard deviations are similar in magnitude and do not exceed 0.10 meters. It is important to note that the Midas absolute accuracy assessment was performed on only one site, which could have had a much smaller bias or slightly larger bias than others in the population of different Midas sites, so we can think of this accuracy assessment as spot-checking to confirm that the claim of 0.3 meters for Midas absolute accuracy (SE90) appears to be reasonable.

Recall that other forms of reference include triangulated aerial frame images, triangulated satellite images, and terrestrial point clouds anchored to surveyed GCPs discussed in [section 2.2.1](#), [section 2.2.2](#), and [section 2.3](#), respectively. While we do not have precisely determined SE90 values for each of these reference sources, the following discussion summarizes what we believe to be reasonable estimates of their accuracy. We begin by stating that a floor exists on the accuracy regardless of the reference source, due to limitations on how well one can know the absolute accuracy of points with respect to the WGS-84 Ellipsoid due to earth tides, crustal motion, ambiguities in datums used in data transformations, etc. The magnitude of this floor is on the order of the 0.1 to 0.3 meter. Triangulated aerial frame images will be at least as good, if not a little better in accuracy compared to Midas data since there is no reliance on dense matching to estimate the depth, or height, component of the points; we can conservatively report 0.1 to 0.3 meters SE90. Triangulated satellite images will have accuracy slightly degraded, compared to triangulated aerial images. Due to the resolution of the satellite images, the precision of manual mensuration from a stereopair would be on the order of 0.3 meters (one Ground Sample Distance, or

Figure 4.0.2: Example of a water tower with a large negative height error (4.5 meters). The level of detail that can be represented in the 3D mesh is coarser than what can be measured in any reference; a typical analyst would recognize the truncated feature and proceed with caution.

GSD) SE90. If we RSS the 0.1 to 0.3 floor with 0.3 from the GSD, we have an estimated accuracy on the order of 0.4 meters from satellite images. Finally, we estimate that the absolute accuracy from terrestrial point cloud data would be similar to that from triangulated aerial frame photographs, or roughly 0.1 to 0.3 meters SE90.

6. Human Measurement Precision

We assessed human measurement precision using measurements of 176 3D points, split evenly between ground and elevated features, from six analysts who each measured the same set of 176 points over the Las Vegas dataset. See [fig. 6.0.1](#) for a summary of the standard deviations in the east and north coordinates, which do not exceed a quarter of a meter. Note the minor impact, across the six analysts, on the total horizontal error compared to the reference.

7. Summary and Conclusions

For “All Points Except Building Corners”, the Maxar 3D textured Mesh product appears to have an SE90 of 2.15 meters, with a confidence level of 0.90. For ground points only, the number drops slightly to 2.00 meters, at the same confidence level. Since these results cover three continents and do not exceed a moderate span in geodetic latitudes, it is important to note that analysis over a wider geographic area

Figure 4.0.3: Example of a building dome with a large negative height error (6.8 meters). The level of detail that can be represented in the 3D mesh, for complex building structures, is coarser than what can be measured in any reference; a typical analyst would recognize the truncated feature and proceed with caution.

Miami results on 17 Surveyed GCPs									
Feature Type	Statistics Type	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)	HR (m)	3DR (m)	LE90 (best est)	CE90 (best est)	SE90 (best est)
SAT – Midas	RMSE	0.73	1.21	0.26	1.41 ^{RMS}	1.44 ^{RMS}	0.47	2.88	2.89
	Signed mean	0.15	-0.99	-0.18	1.23 ^{Mean}	1.26 ^{Mean}			
	Standard Dev	0.73	0.70	0.20					
SAT – GPS	RMSE	0.75	1.19	0.25	1.41	1.43	0.45	2.84	2.85
	Signed mean	0.24	-1.00	-0.13	1.23	1.26			
	Standard Dev	0.74	0.66	0.22					
Midas – GPS	RMSE	0.12	0.10	0.06	0.16	0.17	0.11	0.27	0.28
	Signed mean	0.09	-0.01	0.04	0.14	0.15			
	Standard Dev	0.08	0.10	0.04					

Figure 5.0.1: Absolute accuracy of Midas and Satellite-derived 3D products, compared to surveyed GCPs, shows that the claim of 0.3 meters is reasonable

Six people measured the horizontal coordinates of the same 176 points in the Las Vegas dataset				
Person number	Horizontal Error compared to Reference (meters)		Standard Deviations about the mean measured coordinates (meters)	
	LUB	Best est.	East	North
1	1.01	0.97	0.08	0.21
2	1.00	0.92	0.07	0.24
3	1.07	0.97	0.08	0.19
4	1.17	1.11	0.08	0.23
5	1.04	1.00	0.21	0.19
6	1.22	1.09	0.15	0.24

Figure 6.0.1: Absolute horizontal accuracy and measurement precision as a function of six analysts. The left columns show that assessed absolute accuracy of the product is insensitive to which person performed the measurements, and the right columns show a small variation in measurements from one person to the next, compared to the total horizontal error

would be required in order to corroborate these results.

Magnitudes of errors were consistent across the 25 different sites evaluated. No outliers in the global errors (aka biases) of the products were recognized. The only outliers in the products appeared to be in the surface reconstruction, vice the accuracy of the photogrammetric adjustment of the images, and would likely have been noticed by the analyst during exploitation by inspecting the feature of interest in the context of nearby surrounding features.

We began by showing methodology, including measurement techniques, statistical techniques, and reference data preparation (SOCET GXP Triangulation). We proceeded by introducing the datasets, where reference data consisted of the following types: Midas (Airborne triangulated frame image-derived) 3D mesh, aerial frame images triangulated to surveyed ground control points, USGS Terrestrial Lidar PointCloud data, and UAV acquisition operating with lidar at low altitude. We provided a summary of results for “All points,” “All points except building corners,” and then the other categories. Finally, we performed Monte Carlo simulations to illustrate the variation in results over 20 trials given that a unique selection of five ground points were randomly selected from the total existing sample of measured ground points per site, which ranged from five to 40.

A. Site Data

This appendix contains more detailed information at each of the sites used for testing. At all sites,

- Signed statistics are calculated as ($\epsilon = \text{evaluated} - \text{reference}$); e.g., an “up” value of 1 means the MAXAR satellite-derived product was 1 m above the reference product.
- Accuracy statistics, e.g. LE90, are omitted where there were insufficient samples to calculate them.

A.1. Linköping, Sweden

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Table A.1.1: Linköping, Sweden ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.93	1.01	1.64
Signed Mean	0.76	0.86	-1.38
Standard dev	0.55	0.53	0.88
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.84	1.01	1.45
Signed Mean	0.74	0.86	-1.16
Standard dev	0.40	0.53	0.87
Ground			
RMSE	0.83	0.85	1.37
Signed Mean	0.73	0.72	-1.26
Standard dev	0.40	0.45	0.54
Building Sides			
RMSE	0.87	1.39	1.23
Signed Mean	0.64	1.23	-0.50
Standard dev	0.59	0.67	1.14
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.80	0.80	1.47
Signed Mean	0.79	0.74	-1.42
Standard dev	0.13	0.31	0.39
Building Corners			
RMSE	1.14	1.01	2.05
Signed Mean	0.79	0.87	-1.95
Standard dev	0.82	0.52	0.62
Building Centers			
RMSE	0.98	0.89	2.05
Signed Mean	0.93	0.74	-1.78
Standard dev	0.30	0.53	1.06

Table A.1.2: Linköping, Sweden error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.64	1.38	2.14
Mean	1.48	1.29	2.03
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.32	1.92	2.86
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.63	1.99	3.08
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.45	1.32	1.96
Mean	1.29	1.24	1.87
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.88	1.85	2.44
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.24	1.94	2.83
Ground			
RMS	1.37	1.19	1.81
Mean	1.26	1.14	1.76
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.89	1.62	2.30
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.61	1.80	2.83
Building Sides			
RMS	1.23	1.64	2.05
Mean	1.01	1.52	1.90
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.79	2.43	2.92
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	3.49	2.94	4.50
Building Roofs			
RMS	1.47	1.13	1.85
Mean	1.42	1.10	1.82
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.84	1.47	2.16
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.94	1.79	2.39
Building Corners			
RMS	2.05	1.52	2.55
Mean	1.95	1.41	2.46
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.77	2.13	3.45
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	3.17	2.33	3.88
Building Centers			
RMS	2.05	1.32	2.44
Mean	1.78	1.27	2.27
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.1.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Linköping, Sweden.

Figure A.1.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Linköping, Sweden.

Figure A.1.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Linköping, Sweden.

Figure A.1.4: Signed vertical errors in Linköping, Sweden.

Figure A.1.5: Signed horizontal errors in Linköping, Sweden.

A.2. Kalmar, Sweden

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Table A.2.1: Kalmar, Sweden ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.66	0.61	1.70
Signed Mean	0.18	0.00	-1.43
Standard dev	0.64	0.61	0.92
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.48	0.54	1.42
Signed Mean	0.18	0.07	-1.27
Standard dev	0.45	0.53	0.64
Ground			
RMSE	0.46	0.52	1.38
Signed Mean	0.20	0.08	-1.23
Standard dev	0.42	0.52	0.63
Building Sides			
RMSE	0.44	0.59	1.34
Signed Mean	0.12	0.12	-1.15
Standard dev	0.43	0.59	0.71
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.32	0.39	1.49
Signed Mean	0.24	0.09	-1.46
Standard dev	0.21	0.39	0.29
Building Corners			
RMSE	0.81	0.68	1.95
Signed Mean	0.18	-0.08	-1.59
Standard dev	0.79	0.68	1.13
Building Centers			
RMSE	0.66	0.65	1.45
Signed Mean	0.15	-0.01	-1.18
Standard dev	0.65	0.66	0.84

Table A.2.2: Kalmar, Sweden error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.70	0.90	1.92
Mean	1.57	0.74	1.80
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.37	1.34	2.54
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.55	1.61	2.74
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.42	0.72	1.59
Mean	1.35	0.60	1.53
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.89	1.06	2.13
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.02	1.16	2.23
Ground			
RMS	1.38	0.69	1.54
Mean	1.30	0.64	1.49
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.02	0.98	2.14
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.15	1.08	2.32
Building Sides			
RMS	1.34	0.74	1.53
Mean	1.22	0.65	1.45
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.04	1.08	2.15
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.57	1.61	2.74
Building Roofs			
RMS	1.49	0.50	1.57
Mean	1.46	0.42	1.54
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.85	0.84	2.04
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.10	1.15	2.20
Building Corners			
RMS	1.95	1.06	2.22
Mean	1.79	0.88	2.08
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.74	1.80	3.08
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	3.01	1.99	3.47
Building Centers			
RMS	1.45	0.93	1.72
Mean	1.41	0.74	1.64
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.90	1.43	2.32
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.02	2.69	3.37

Figure A.2.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Kalmar, Sweden.

Figure A.2.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Kalmar, Sweden.

Figure A.2.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Kalmar, Sweden.

Figure A.2.4: Signed vertical errors in Kalmar, Sweden.

Figure A.2.5: Signed horizontal errors in Kalmar, Sweden.

A.3. Miami, USA

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Table A.3.1: Miami, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.47	1.02	1.04
Signed Mean	0.05	-0.92	-0.34
Standard dev	0.47	0.45	0.98
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.43	1.08	0.86
Signed Mean	0.07	-1.03	-0.24
Standard dev	0.42	0.32	0.83
Ground			
RMSE	0.29	1.21	0.58
Signed Mean	0.08	-1.18	-0.22
Standard dev	0.28	0.25	0.54
Building Sides			
RMSE	0.63	0.99	0.96
Signed Mean	0.16	-0.92	-0.08
Standard dev	0.62	0.36	0.97
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.21	1.06	0.93
Signed Mean	-0.02	-1.04	-0.33
Standard dev	0.21	0.21	0.88
Building Corners			
RMSE	0.60	0.76	1.56
Signed Mean	-0.05	-0.48	-0.74
Standard dev	0.61	0.60	1.39
Building Centers			
RMSE	0.55	0.91	1.12
Signed Mean	0.01	-0.79	-0.61
Standard dev	0.59	0.50	1.01

Table A.3.2: Miami, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.04	1.13	1.53
Mean	0.77	1.07	1.41
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.53	1.53	2.07
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.99	1.64	2.21
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	0.86	1.16	1.44
Mean	0.67	1.12	1.38
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.33	1.54	1.85
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.57	1.66	2.07
Ground			
RMS	0.58	1.24	1.37
Mean	0.47	1.21	1.34
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.96	1.62	1.72
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.16	1.79	1.79
Building Sides			
RMS	0.96	1.17	1.52
Mean	0.81	1.11	1.44
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.55	1.62	2.05
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.76	2.00	2.43
Building Roofs			
RMS	0.93	1.08	1.42
Mean	0.66	1.06	1.33
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.22	1.37	1.74
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.92	1.46	2.51
Building Corners			
RMS	1.56	0.97	1.84
Mean	1.17	0.87	1.56
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.95	1.51	3.23
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	4.13	2.21	4.20
Building Centers			
RMS	1.12	1.07	1.55
Mean	0.95	1.02	1.45
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.3.1: Vertical errors of measurements in Miami, USA.

Figure A.3.2: Horizontal errors of measurements in Miami, USA.

Figure A.3.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Miami, USA.

Figure A.3.4: Signed vertical errors in Miami, USA.

Figure A.3.5: Signed horizontal errors in Miami, USA.

A.4. San Antonio, USA

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Table A.4.1: San Antonio, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.96	0.46	0.75
Signed Mean	0.80	-0.10	-0.24
Standard dev	0.53	0.45	0.71
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.93	0.42	0.67
Signed Mean	0.87	-0.17	-0.13
Standard dev	0.33	0.38	0.66
Ground			
RMSE	0.97	0.38	0.48
Signed Mean	0.94	-0.26	-0.32
Standard dev	0.24	0.27	0.37
Building Sides			
RMSE	0.92	0.46	0.85
Signed Mean	0.84	-0.31	0.34
Standard dev	0.39	0.35	0.79
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.95	0.42	0.64
Signed Mean	0.92	0.01	-0.37
Standard dev	0.26	0.42	0.52
Building Corners			
RMSE	1.09	0.61	0.98
Signed Mean	0.58	0.14	-0.61
Standard dev	0.94	0.60	0.78
Building Centers			
RMSE	0.57	0.36	0.62
Signed Mean	0.46	0.11	-0.31
Standard dev	0.36	0.36	0.57

Table A.4.2: San Antonio, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	0.75	1.07	1.31
Mean	0.56	1.01	1.23
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.33	1.33	1.81
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.51	1.53	2.03
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	0.67	1.01	1.22
Mean	0.49	0.98	1.16
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.16	1.26	1.62
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.44	1.30	1.78
Ground			
RMS	0.48	1.04	1.15
Mean	0.34	1.01	1.11
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.79	1.28	1.49
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.34	1.40	1.68
Building Sides			
RMS	0.85	1.03	1.33
Mean	0.68	0.99	1.26
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.44	1.27	1.89
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.61	1.58	2.38
Building Roofs			
RMS	0.64	1.04	1.22
Mean	0.47	1.02	1.17
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.05	1.27	1.70
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.65	1.39	1.84
Building Corners			
RMS	0.98	1.25	1.59
Mean	0.78	1.12	1.48
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.55	2.19	2.41
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.81	2.43	3.12
Building Centers			
RMS	0.62	0.67	0.91
Mean	0.42	0.64	0.85
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.4.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in San Antonio, USA.

Figure A.4.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in San Antonio, USA.

Figure A.4.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in San Antonio, USA.

Figure A.4.4: Signed vertical errors in San Antonio, USA.

Figure A.4.5: Signed horizontal errors in San Antonio, USA.

A.5. Chicago, USA

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Table A.5.1: Chicago, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.49	0.65	0.69
Signed Mean	-0.02	-0.30	0.34
Standard dev	0.49	0.58	0.61
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.43	0.58	0.75
Signed Mean	-0.01	-0.30	0.44
Standard dev	0.43	0.50	0.61
Ground			
RMSE	0.47	0.66	0.60
Signed Mean	-0.08	-0.34	0.56
Standard dev	0.46	0.57	0.22
Building Sides			
RMSE	0.40	0.55	1.09
Signed Mean	-0.06	-0.28	0.56
Standard dev	0.40	0.48	0.95
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.42	0.55	0.40
Signed Mean	0.08	-0.28	0.28
Standard dev	0.42	0.48	0.29
Building Corners			
RMSE	0.66	0.84	0.43
Signed Mean	-0.07	-0.30	-0.04
Standard dev	0.66	0.80	0.43
Building Centers			
RMSE	0.41	0.49	0.67
Signed Mean	0.16	-0.23	0.15
Standard dev	0.40	0.46	0.69

Table A.5.2: Chicago, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	0.69	0.81	1.07
Mean	0.51	0.71	0.96
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.95	1.21	1.47
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.24	1.32	1.56
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	0.75	0.72	1.04
Mean	0.57	0.64	0.93
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.05	1.10	1.37
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.36	1.18	1.56
Ground			
RMS	0.60	0.80	1.00
Mean	0.56	0.72	0.96
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.80	1.19	1.34
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	0.85	1.41	1.55
Building Sides			
RMS	1.09	0.68	1.29
Mean	0.82	0.61	1.10
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.84	0.97	2.00
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.41	1.31	2.64
Building Roofs			
RMS	0.40	0.70	0.80
Mean	0.35	0.60	0.74
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.61	1.09	1.17
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	0.78	1.26	1.32
Building Corners			
RMS	0.43	1.07	1.15
Mean	0.32	0.98	1.08
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.80	1.62	1.63
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.24	1.79	2.03
Building Centers			
RMS	0.67	0.64	0.93
Mean	0.54	0.61	0.87
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.5.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Chicago, USA.

Figure A.5.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Chicago, USA.

Figure A.5.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Chicago, USA.

Figure A.5.4: Signed vertical errors in Chicago, USA.

Figure A.5.5: Signed horizontal errors in Chicago, USA.

A.6. New York, USA

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Note: some outliers are still under investigation (pts 202 and 208, and 434, have very large outliers, removed from the plots).

Table A.6.1: New York, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.80	0.76	1.10
Signed Mean	-0.49	-0.43	-0.59
Standard dev	0.64	0.64	0.94
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.73	0.72	0.96
Signed Mean	-0.52	-0.44	-0.41
Standard dev	0.52	0.57	0.87
Ground			
RMSE	0.55	0.79	0.66
Signed Mean	-0.38	-0.63	-0.15
Standard dev	0.39	0.48	0.65
Building Sides			
RMSE	0.95	0.77	1.07
Signed Mean	-0.66	-0.25	-0.61
Standard dev	0.69	0.74	0.90
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.67	0.57	0.96
Signed Mean	-0.57	-0.46	-0.68
Standard dev	0.35	0.33	0.69
Building Corners			
RMSE	1.03	0.93	1.53
Signed Mean	-0.39	-0.39	-1.26
Standard dev	0.97	0.86	0.88
Building Centers			
RMSE	0.68	0.72	1.52
Signed Mean	-0.23	-0.21	0.54
Standard dev	0.68	0.74	1.52

Table A.6.2: New York, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.10	1.11	1.56
Mean	0.83	0.99	1.40
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.79	1.73	2.35
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.05	1.87	2.55
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	0.96	1.02	1.41
Mean	0.71	0.94	1.28
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.58	1.48	2.11
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.95	1.73	2.33
Ground			
RMS	0.66	0.96	1.17
Mean	0.40	0.91	1.07
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.63	1.37	1.53
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.45	1.53	1.68
Building Sides			
RMS	1.07	1.22	1.63
Mean	0.92	1.09	1.53
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.69	1.93	2.34
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.99	2.12	2.47
Building Roofs			
RMS	0.96	0.87	1.30
Mean	0.78	0.83	1.22
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.76	1.15	1.96
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.14	1.34	2.43
Building Corners			
RMS	1.53	1.39	2.07
Mean	1.29	1.20	1.88
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.62	2.26	2.92
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	3.43	3.09	4.33
Building Centers			
RMS	1.52	0.99	1.81
Mean	0.94	0.92	1.52
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.6.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in New York, USA.

Figure A.6.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in New York, USA.

Figure A.6.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in New York, USA.

Figure A.6.4: Signed vertical errors in New York, USA.

Figure A.6.5: Signed horizontal errors in New York, USA.

A.7. Orlando, USA

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Table A.7.1: Orlando, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.50	0.53	0.62
Signed Mean	-0.21	-0.29	-0.32
Standard dev	0.45	0.44	0.53
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.49	0.47	0.64
Signed Mean	-0.23	-0.26	-0.35
Standard dev	0.44	0.40	0.54
Ground			
RMSE	0.47	0.49	0.37
Signed Mean	-0.20	-0.27	-0.15
Standard dev	0.43	0.41	0.34
Building Sides			
RMSE	0.49	0.45	0.90
Signed Mean	-0.28	-0.30	-0.49
Standard dev	0.41	0.34	0.76
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.47	0.46	0.62
Signed Mean	-0.23	-0.20	-0.45
Standard dev	0.41	0.42	0.43
Building Corners			
RMSE	0.52	0.69	0.51
Signed Mean	-0.12	-0.39	-0.22
Standard dev	0.51	0.58	0.47
Building Centers			
RMSE	0.70	0.55	0.21
Signed Mean	-0.18	-0.31	-0.18
Standard dev	0.72	0.48	0.11

Table A.7.2: Orlando, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	0.62	0.73	0.95
Mean	0.46	0.63	0.85
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.01	1.06	1.33
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.10	1.17	1.42
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	0.64	0.68	0.94
Mean	0.47	0.60	0.83
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.04	1.01	1.32
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.16	1.17	1.42
Ground			
RMS	0.37	0.68	0.77
Mean	0.27	0.58	0.69
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.54	1.01	1.29
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.02	1.26	1.41
Building Sides			
RMS	0.90	0.66	1.12
Mean	0.73	0.61	1.01
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.23	0.97	1.45
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.57	1.17	1.75
Building Roofs			
RMS	0.62	0.65	0.90
Mean	0.48	0.58	0.83
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.10	1.07	1.32
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.24	1.29	1.49
Building Corners			
RMS	0.51	0.86	1.00
Mean	0.43	0.76	0.93
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.82	1.31	1.40
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	0.92	2.05	2.05
Building Centers			
RMS	0.21	0.89	0.92
Mean	0.18	0.69	0.74
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.7.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Orlando, USA.

Figure A.7.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Orlando, USA.

Figure A.7.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Orlando, USA.

Figure A.7.4: Signed vertical errors in Orlando, USA.

Figure A.7.5: Signed horizontal errors in Orlando, USA.

A.8. Weymouth, GBR

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Table A.8.1: Weymouth, GBR ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.46	0.49	0.76
Signed Mean	0.04	-0.01	0.58
Standard dev	0.46	0.49	0.50
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.29	0.37	0.74
Signed Mean	0.05	-0.06	0.57
Standard dev	0.28	0.36	0.48
Ground			
RMSE	0.31	0.36	0.74
Signed Mean	0.12	-0.18	0.52
Standard dev	0.28	0.32	0.53
Building Sides			
RMSE	0.27	0.30	0.81
Signed Mean	-0.15	-0.03	0.76
Standard dev	0.24	0.32	0.30
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.22	0.30	0.72
Signed Mean	0.05	0.08	0.61
Standard dev	0.21	0.29	0.38
Building Corners			
RMSE	0.87	0.81	0.85
Signed Mean	0.01	0.23	0.61
Standard dev	0.90	0.80	0.60
Building Centers			
RMSE	0.47	0.70	0.76
Signed Mean	-0.26	-0.05	0.37
Standard dev	0.44	0.79	0.74

Table A.8.2: Weymouth, GBR error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	0.76	0.67	1.01
Mean	0.65	0.52	0.91
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.14	1.17	1.45
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.21	1.45	1.76
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	0.74	0.46	0.87
Mean	0.64	0.38	0.81
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.07	0.76	1.16
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.16	0.86	1.41
Ground			
RMS	0.74	0.47	0.88
Mean	0.61	0.40	0.80
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.18	0.79	1.29
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.43	0.90	1.45
Building Sides			
RMS	0.81	0.40	0.90
Mean	0.76	0.36	0.87
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Building Roofs			
RMS	0.72	0.37	0.80
Mean	0.65	0.31	0.76
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.03	0.59	1.07
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.11	0.85	1.26
Building Corners			
RMS	0.85	1.19	1.47
Mean	0.71	1.10	1.34
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Building Centers			
RMS	0.76	0.85	1.14
Mean	0.68	0.76	1.11
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.8.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Weymouth, GBR.

Figure A.8.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Weymouth, GBR.

Figure A.8.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Weymouth, GBR.

Figure A.8.4: Signed vertical errors in Weymouth, GBR.

Figure A.8.5: Signed horizontal errors in Weymouth, GBR.

A.9. Las Vegas, USA

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Table A.9.1: Las Vegas, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.50	0.34	1.06
Signed Mean	0.34	0.08	-0.89
Standard dev	0.36	0.33	0.59
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.50	0.34	1.06
Signed Mean	0.34	0.08	-0.89
Standard dev	0.36	0.33	0.59
Ground			
RMSE	0.46	0.31	0.85
Signed Mean	0.38	0.00	-0.75
Standard dev	0.26	0.32	0.40
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.53	0.37	1.24
Signed Mean	0.31	0.16	-1.02
Standard dev	0.44	0.33	0.71

Table A.9.2: Las Vegas, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.06	0.60	1.22
Mean	0.95	0.54	1.12
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.53	0.79	1.60
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.64	0.84	1.76
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.06	0.60	1.22
Mean	0.95	0.54	1.12
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.53	0.79	1.60
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.64	0.84	1.76
Ground			
RMS	0.85	0.55	1.02
Mean	0.79	0.52	0.97
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.14	0.72	1.35
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.41	0.84	1.47
Building Roofs			
RMS	1.24	0.65	1.40
Mean	1.11	0.56	1.27
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.66	0.83	1.80
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.81	0.97	1.87

Figure A.9.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Las Vegas, USA.

Figure A.9.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Las Vegas, USA.

Figure A.9.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Las Vegas, USA.

Figure A.9.4: Signed vertical errors in Las Vegas, USA.

Figure A.9.5: Signed horizontal errors in Las Vegas, USA.

A.10. Hoover Dam, USA

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Table A.10.1: Hoover Dam, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.46	0.56	1.09
Signed Mean	0.21	0.22	-0.97
Standard dev	0.41	0.51	0.49
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.39	0.47	1.09
Signed Mean	0.23	0.25	-0.97
Standard dev	0.32	0.40	0.51
Ground			
RMSE	0.39	0.49	1.06
Signed Mean	0.23	0.27	-0.95
Standard dev	0.32	0.42	0.46
Building Sides			
RMSE	0.44	0.25	0.76
Signed Mean	0.40	0.10	-0.70
Standard dev	0.20	0.28	0.35
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.41	0.46	1.38
Signed Mean	0.27	0.32	-1.23
Standard dev	0.33	0.35	0.66
Building Corners			
RMSE	0.68	0.85	1.07
Signed Mean	0.09	0.09	-0.99
Standard dev	0.70	0.89	0.41
Building Centers			
RMSE	0.37	0.26	0.64
Signed Mean	0.00	-0.16	-0.51
Standard dev	0.46	0.26	0.48

Table A.10.2: Hoover Dam, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.09	0.72	1.30
Mean	0.97	0.64	1.20
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.60	1.03	1.82
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.06	1.20	2.20
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.09	0.61	1.25
Mean	0.97	0.57	1.15
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.69	0.90	1.82
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.13	1.03	2.24
Ground			
RMS	1.06	0.63	1.23
Mean	0.95	0.58	1.14
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.69	0.91	1.82
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.13	1.04	2.24
Building Sides			
RMS	0.76	0.50	0.91
Mean	0.70	0.48	0.90
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Building Roofs			
RMS	1.38	0.62	1.51
Mean	1.23	0.58	1.38
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Building Corners			
RMS	1.07	1.09	1.52
Mean	0.99	0.95	1.48
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Building Centers			
RMS	0.64	0.46	0.79
Mean	0.51	0.45	0.74
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.10.1: Vertical error samples in Hoover Dam, USA.

Figure A.10.2: Horizontal (radial) error samples in Hoover Dam, USA.

Figure A.10.3: 3D radial error samples in Hoover Dam, USA.

Figure A.10.4: Signed vertical errors in Hoover Dam, USA.

Figure A.10.5: Signed horizontal errors in Hoover Dam, USA.

A.11. Lolldaiga, Kenya

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Table A.11.1: Lolldaiga, Kenya ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	1.00	0.68	1.36
Signed Mean	-0.81	0.31	-1.17
Standard dev	0.59	0.61	0.69
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	1.00	0.68	1.36
Signed Mean	-0.81	0.31	-1.17
Standard dev	0.59	0.61	0.69
Ground			
RMSE	1.12	0.86	1.34
Signed Mean	-0.81	0.52	-1.10
Standard dev	0.78	0.70	0.78
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.87	0.42	1.37
Signed Mean	-0.81	0.10	-1.24
Standard dev	0.31	0.41	0.59

Table A.11.2: Lolldaiga, Kenya error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.36	1.21	1.82
Mean	1.19	1.08	1.70
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.18	1.72	2.68
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.65	2.21	3.00
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.36	1.21	1.82
Mean	1.19	1.08	1.70
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.18	1.72	2.68
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.65	2.21	3.00
Ground			
RMS	1.34	1.41	1.95
Mean	1.13	1.24	1.79
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.38	2.36	2.96
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.68	2.78	3.34
Building Roofs			
RMS	1.37	0.96	1.68
Mean	1.24	0.91	1.60
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.19	1.28	2.32
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.27	1.51	2.57

Figure A.11.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Lolldaiga, Kenya.

Figure A.11.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Lolldaiga, Kenya.

Figure A.11.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Lolldaiga, Kenya.

Figure A.11.4: Signed vertical errors in Lolldaiga, Kenya.

Figure A.11.5: Signed horizontal errors in Lolldaiga, Kenya.

A.12. Ol Maisor, Kenya

The reference at this site was built from the MIDAS system, which derives an airborne textured mesh; see [section 2.1](#).

Table A.12.1: Ol Maisor, Kenya ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.57	0.76	1.21
Signed Mean	0.00	0.31	0.20
Standard dev	0.58	0.69	1.21
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.57	0.76	1.21
Signed Mean	0.00	0.31	0.20
Standard dev	0.58	0.69	1.21
Ground			
RMSE	0.53	0.77	1.27
Signed Mean	-0.01	0.40	0.25
Standard dev	0.54	0.67	1.26
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.71	0.68	1.00
Signed Mean	0.05	-0.02	0.00
Standard dev	0.74	0.72	1.05

Table A.12.2: Ol Maisor, Kenya error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.21	0.95	1.54
Mean	1.02	0.78	1.40
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.87	1.55	2.12
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.32	1.88	2.73
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.21	0.95	1.54
Mean	1.02	0.78	1.40
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.87	1.55	2.12
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.32	1.88	2.73
Ground			
RMS	1.27	0.94	1.58
Mean	1.08	0.77	1.44
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.97	1.55	2.40
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.32	1.80	2.73
Building Roofs			
RMS	1.00	0.99	1.40
Mean	0.78	0.81	1.25
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.12.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Ol Maisor, Kenya.

Figure A.12.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Ol Maisor, Kenya.

Figure A.12.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Ol Maisor, Kenya.

Figure A.12.4: Signed vertical errors in Ol Maisor, Kenya.

Figure A.12.5: Signed horizontal errors in Ol Maisor, Kenya.

A.13. Fayetteville, AR, USA

The reference at this site was built from triangulated, high-resolution, airborne frame images as described in [section 2.2.1](#).

Table A.13.1: Fayetteville, AR, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.36	0.43	1.81
Signed Mean	0.17	0.27	-1.74
Standard dev	0.32	0.33	0.52
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.36	0.43	1.81
Signed Mean	0.17	0.27	-1.74
Standard dev	0.32	0.33	0.52
Ground			
RMSE	0.35	0.45	1.60
Signed Mean	0.16	0.33	-1.55
Standard dev	0.31	0.30	0.38
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.37	0.40	2.00
Signed Mean	0.18	0.22	-1.92
Standard dev	0.32	0.34	0.58

Table A.13.2: Fayetteville, AR, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.81	0.56	1.89
Mean	1.74	0.47	1.82
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.41	0.80	2.61
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.79	0.88	2.89
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.81	0.56	1.89
Mean	1.74	0.47	1.82
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.41	0.80	2.61
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.79	0.88	2.89
Ground			
RMS	1.60	0.57	1.69
Mean	1.55	0.51	1.65
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.90	0.82	1.99
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.22	0.88	2.27
Building Roofs			
RMS	2.00	0.55	2.08
Mean	1.92	0.44	1.99
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.78	0.81	2.91
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.94	1.24	3.04

Figure A.13.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Fayetteville, AR, USA.

Figure A.13.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Fayetteville, AR, USA.

Figure A.13.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Fayetteville, AR, USA.

Figure A.13.4: Signed vertical errors in Fayetteville, AR, USA.

Figure A.13.5: Signed horizontal errors in Fayetteville, AR, USA.

A.14. Bentonville, AR, USA

The reference at this site was built from triangulated, high-resolution, airborne frame images as described in [section 2.2.1](#).

No points on buildings were measured in Bentonville, so all points are in the “ground” category.

Table A.14.1: Bentonville, AR, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.54	0.33	1.13
Signed Mean	0.44	0.17	-1.01
Standard dev	0.32	0.29	0.52
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.54	0.33	1.13
Signed Mean	0.44	0.17	-1.01
Standard dev	0.32	0.29	0.52
Ground			
RMSE	0.54	0.33	1.13
Signed Mean	0.44	0.17	-1.01
Standard dev	0.32	0.29	0.52

Table A.14.2: Bentonville, AR, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.13	0.64	1.30
Mean	1.08	0.59	1.26
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.69	0.97	1.79
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.87	1.00	1.94
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.13	0.64	1.30
Mean	1.08	0.59	1.26
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.69	0.97	1.79
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.87	1.00	1.94
Ground			
RMS	1.13	0.64	1.30
Mean	1.08	0.59	1.26
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.69	0.97	1.79
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.87	1.00	1.94

Figure A.14.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Bentonville, AR, USA.

Figure A.14.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Bentonville, AR, USA.

Figure A.14.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Bentonville, AR, USA.

Figure A.14.4: Signed vertical errors in Bentonville, AR, USA.

Figure A.14.5: Signed horizontal errors in Bentonville, AR, USA.

A.15. Ardmore, OK, USA

The reference at this site was built from triangulated, high-resolution, airborne frame images as described in [section 2.2.1](#).

Table A.15.1: Ardmore, OK, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	1.11	0.88	1.73
Signed Mean	-1.03	0.79	-1.44
Standard dev	0.41	0.39	0.96
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	1.11	0.88	1.73
Signed Mean	-1.03	0.79	-1.44
Standard dev	0.41	0.39	0.96
Ground			
RMSE	1.13	0.83	1.03
Signed Mean	-1.00	0.77	-0.94
Standard dev	0.54	0.32	0.43
Building Roofs			
RMSE	1.08	0.92	2.20
Signed Mean	-1.06	0.80	-1.93
Standard dev	0.24	0.45	1.07

Table A.15.2: Ardmore, OK, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.73	1.41	2.23
Mean	1.45	1.37	2.07
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.30	1.73	2.93
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.91	2.09	3.29
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.73	1.41	2.23
Mean	1.45	1.37	2.07
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.30	1.73	2.93
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.91	2.09	3.29
Ground			
RMS	1.03	1.40	1.74
Mean	0.96	1.36	1.70
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.31	1.73	2.24
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.53	2.09	2.49
Building Roofs			
RMS	2.20	1.42	2.62
Mean	1.93	1.38	2.43
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.78	1.95	3.29
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	4.51	2.22	4.91

Figure A.15.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Ardmore, OK, USA.

Figure A.15.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Ardmore, OK, USA.

Figure A.15.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Ardmore, OK, USA.

Figure A.15.4: Signed vertical errors in Ardmore, OK, USA.

Figure A.15.5: Signed horizontal errors in Ardmore, OK, USA.

A.16. Little Rock, AR, USA

The reference at this site was built from triangulated, high-resolution, airborne frame images as described in [section 2.2.1](#).

Table A.16.1: Little Rock, AR, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.41	0.47	0.94
Signed Mean	-0.06	0.29	-0.81
Standard dev	0.41	0.37	0.48
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.41	0.47	0.94
Signed Mean	-0.06	0.29	-0.81
Standard dev	0.41	0.37	0.48
Ground			
RMSE	0.27	0.46	0.75
Signed Mean	-0.06	0.31	-0.63
Standard dev	0.27	0.34	0.41
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.52	0.48	1.09
Signed Mean	-0.07	0.27	-0.98
Standard dev	0.52	0.40	0.48

Table A.16.2: Little Rock, AR, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	0.94	0.63	1.13
Mean	0.82	0.50	1.03
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.45	0.80	1.59
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.68	1.03	1.81
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	0.94	0.63	1.13
Mean	0.82	0.50	1.03
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.45	0.80	1.59
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.68	1.03	1.81
Ground			
RMS	0.75	0.53	0.92
Mean	0.66	0.47	0.87
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.14	0.82	1.33
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.45	1.02	1.46
Building Roofs			
RMS	1.09	0.71	1.30
Mean	0.98	0.52	1.18
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.69	0.91	1.82
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.95	1.35	2.26

Figure A.16.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Little Rock, AR, USA.

Figure A.16.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Little Rock, AR, USA.

Figure A.16.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Little Rock, AR, USA.

Figure A.16.4: Signed vertical errors in Little Rock, AR, USA.

Figure A.16.5: Signed horizontal errors in Little Rock, AR, USA.

A.17. Hamburg, AR, USA

The reference at this site was built from triangulated, high-resolution, airborne frame images as described in [section 2.2.1](#).

Table A.17.1: Hamburg, AR, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.50	0.74	1.28
Signed Mean	0.25	0.61	0.19
Standard dev	0.44	0.42	1.28
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.50	0.74	1.28
Signed Mean	0.25	0.61	0.19
Standard dev	0.44	0.42	1.28
Ground			
RMSE	0.43	0.83	1.24
Signed Mean	0.26	0.68	0.69
Standard dev	0.35	0.48	1.05
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.56	0.62	1.32
Signed Mean	0.24	0.53	-0.34
Standard dev	0.52	0.34	1.30

Table A.17.2: Hamburg, AR, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.28	0.89	1.56
Mean	1.08	0.78	1.42
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.92	1.26	2.25
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.39	1.70	2.83
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.28	0.89	1.56
Mean	1.08	0.78	1.42
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.92	1.26	2.25
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.39	1.70	2.83
Ground			
RMS	1.24	0.93	1.56
Mean	1.06	0.83	1.44
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.01	1.49	2.26
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.39	1.84	2.45
Building Roofs			
RMS	1.32	0.84	1.57
Mean	1.10	0.74	1.40
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.92	1.25	2.27
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.68	1.53	3.03

Figure A.17.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Hamburg, AR, USA.

Figure A.17.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Hamburg, AR, USA.

Figure A.17.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Hamburg, AR, USA.

Figure A.17.4: Signed vertical errors in Hamburg, AR, USA.

Figure A.17.5: Signed horizontal errors in Hamburg, AR, USA.

A.18. Jonesboro, AR, USA

The reference at this site was built from triangulated, high-resolution, airborne frame images as described in [section 2.2.1](#).

Table A.18.1: Jonesboro, AR, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.26	0.73	0.44
Signed Mean	-0.15	-0.65	0.11
Standard dev	0.22	0.34	0.43
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.26	0.73	0.44
Signed Mean	-0.15	-0.65	0.11
Standard dev	0.22	0.34	0.43
Ground			
RMSE	0.29	0.78	0.37
Signed Mean	-0.21	-0.72	0.26
Standard dev	0.20	0.30	0.27
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.20	0.63	0.54
Signed Mean	-0.04	-0.50	-0.19
Standard dev	0.20	0.38	0.52

Table A.18.2: Jonesboro, AR, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	0.44	0.78	0.89
Mean	0.34	0.72	0.83
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.57	1.07	1.15
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	0.68	1.15	1.21
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	0.44	0.78	0.89
Mean	0.34	0.72	0.83
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.57	1.07	1.15
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	0.68	1.15	1.21
Ground			
RMS	0.37	0.83	0.91
Mean	0.32	0.79	0.87
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.56	1.13	1.15
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	0.67	1.17	1.21
Building Roofs			
RMS	0.54	0.66	0.85
Mean	0.37	0.58	0.76
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.18.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Jonesboro, AR, USA.

Figure A.18.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Jonesboro, AR, USA.

Figure A.18.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Jonesboro, AR, USA.

Figure A.18.4: Signed vertical errors in Jonesboro, AR, USA.

Figure A.18.5: Signed horizontal errors in Jonesboro, AR, USA.

A.19. Texarkana, AR, USA

The reference at this site was built from triangulated, high-resolution, airborne frame images as described in [section 2.2.1](#).

Table A.19.1: Texarkana, AR, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.48	0.29	1.50
Signed Mean	-0.11	0.00	-1.37
Standard dev	0.48	0.29	0.62
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.48	0.29	1.50
Signed Mean	-0.11	0.00	-1.37
Standard dev	0.48	0.29	0.62
Ground			
RMSE	0.64	0.25	1.10
Signed Mean	-0.07	-0.02	-1.06
Standard dev	0.65	0.26	0.27
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.25	0.31	1.81
Signed Mean	-0.14	0.02	-1.67
Standard dev	0.21	0.32	0.72

Table A.19.2: Texarkana, AR, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.50	0.56	1.60
Mean	1.37	0.39	1.47
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.19	0.72	2.31
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.87	0.80	2.98
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.50	0.56	1.60
Mean	1.37	0.39	1.47
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	2.19	0.72	2.31
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	2.87	0.80	2.98
Ground			
RMS	1.10	0.69	1.29
Mean	1.06	0.45	1.23
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Building Roofs			
RMS	1.81	0.40	1.85
Mean	1.67	0.33	1.72
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.19.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Texarkana, AR, USA.

Figure A.19.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Texarkana, AR, USA.

Figure A.19.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Texarkana, AR, USA.

Figure A.19.4: Signed vertical errors in Texarkana, AR, USA.

A.20. Benton, AR, USA

The reference at this site was built from triangulated, high-resolution, airborne frame images as described in [section 2.2.1](#).

Table A.20.1: Benton, AR, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.32	0.46	0.57
Signed Mean	0.05	-0.28	-0.03
Standard dev	0.32	0.37	0.58
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.32	0.46	0.57
Signed Mean	0.05	-0.28	-0.03
Standard dev	0.32	0.37	0.58
Ground			
RMSE	0.40	0.49	0.42
Signed Mean	0.08	-0.32	0.30
Standard dev	0.39	0.38	0.29
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.23	0.42	0.70
Signed Mean	0.02	-0.23	-0.36
Standard dev	0.23	0.35	0.60

Table A.20.2: Benton, AR, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	0.57	0.56	0.80
Mean	0.45	0.48	0.73
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.02	0.85	1.19
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.13	1.03	1.32
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	0.57	0.56	0.80
Mean	0.45	0.48	0.73
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.02	0.85	1.19
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.13	1.03	1.32
Ground			
RMS	0.42	0.63	0.76
Mean	0.34	0.56	0.71
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.67	0.99	1.08
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	0.73	1.23	1.23
Building Roofs			
RMS	0.70	0.48	0.85
Mean	0.55	0.41	0.76
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.19	0.79	1.31
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.29	0.90	1.45

Figure A.20.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Benton, AR, USA.

Figure A.20.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Benton, AR, USA.

Figure A.20.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Benton, AR, USA.

Figure A.20.4: Signed vertical errors in Benton, AR, USA.

Figure A.20.5: Signed horizontal errors in Benton, AR, USA.

A.21. Fort Bragg, USA

The reference at this site was built from triangulated, high-resolution, airborne frame images as described in [section 2.2.1](#).

Table A.21.1: Fort Bragg, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	1.11	0.66	0.60
Signed Mean	0.91	0.22	0.05
Standard dev	0.63	0.63	0.60
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	1.10	0.59	0.52
Signed Mean	0.91	0.14	0.18
Standard dev	0.62	0.58	0.49
Ground			
RMSE	1.12	0.51	0.51
Signed Mean	0.89	-0.05	0.29
Standard dev	0.69	0.51	0.43
Building Roofs			
RMSE	0.91	0.73	0.45
Signed Mean	0.83	0.52	0.07
Standard dev	0.38	0.53	0.46
Building Corners			
RMSE	1.12	0.89	0.85
Signed Mean	0.91	0.56	-0.44
Standard dev	0.67	0.71	0.74
Building Centers			
RMSE	1.65	0.54	0.79
Signed Mean	1.58	0.11	-0.34
Standard dev	0.52	0.58	0.78

Table A.21.2: Fort Bragg, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	0.60	1.29	1.42
Mean	0.43	1.18	1.31
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.97	1.85	1.98
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.15	2.15	2.29
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	0.52	1.25	1.35
Mean	0.36	1.15	1.24
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.75	1.72	1.90
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.01	2.15	2.29
Ground			
RMS	0.51	1.23	1.34
Mean	0.35	1.11	1.21
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.68	1.73	1.90
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	0.94	2.28	2.40
Building Roofs			
RMS	0.45	1.17	1.25
Mean	0.32	1.13	1.19
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	0.73	1.51	1.66
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.43	2.13	2.56
Building Corners			
RMS	0.85	1.43	1.66
Mean	0.70	1.30	1.58
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	1.56	2.16	2.22
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	1.83	2.63	2.73
Building Centers			
RMS	0.79	1.74	1.91
Mean	0.60	1.68	1.87
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.21.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Fort Bragg, USA.

Figure A.21.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Fort Bragg, USA.

Figure A.21.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Fort Bragg, USA.

Figure A.21.4: Signed vertical errors in Fort Bragg, USA.

Figure A.21.5: Signed horizontal errors in Fort Bragg, USA.

A.22. Montpelier, VA, USA

The reference product at this site is a point cloud generated by UAV-mounted lidar; see [section 2.3](#) for details.

Table A.22.1: Montpelier, VA, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.59	0.64	2.14
Signed Mean	-0.22	-0.09	-2.10
Standard dev	0.57	0.66	0.44
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.59	0.61	1.94
Signed Mean	-0.31	-0.18	-1.93
Standard dev	0.53	0.62	0.28
Ground			
RMSE	0.59	0.61	1.94
Signed Mean	-0.31	-0.18	-1.93
Standard dev	0.53	0.62	0.28
Building Corners			
RMSE	0.61	0.70	2.53
Signed Mean	-0.01	0.10	-2.50
Standard dev	0.70	0.80	0.51

Table A.22.2: Montpelier, VA, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	2.14	0.87	2.31
Mean	2.10	0.76	2.27
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.94	0.85	2.12
Mean	1.93	0.72	2.11
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Ground			
RMS	1.94	0.85	2.12
Mean	1.93	0.72	2.11
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Building Corners			
RMS	2.53	0.93	2.70
Mean	2.50	0.84	2.65
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.22.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Montpelier, VA, USA.

Figure A.22.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Montpelier, VA, USA.

Figure A.22.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Montpelier, VA, USA.

Figure A.22.4: Signed vertical errors in Montpelier, VA, USA.

Figure A.22.5: Signed horizontal errors in Montpelier, VA, USA.

A.23. Northeastern Illinois, USA

The reference product at this site is a point cloud generated by terrestrial lidar; see [section 2.3](#) for details.

Table A.23.1: Northeastern Illinois, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	1.42	0.63	1.46
Signed Mean	-1.28	-0.57	1.28
Standard dev	0.64	0.29	0.75
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	1.42	0.63	1.46
Signed Mean	-1.28	-0.57	1.28
Standard dev	0.64	0.29	0.75
Ground			
RMSE	1.34	0.60	1.98
Signed Mean	-1.33	-0.58	1.98
Standard dev	0.11	0.17	0.17
Building Roofs			
RMSE	1.48	0.66	0.80
Signed Mean	-1.24	-0.56	0.69
Standard dev	0.89	0.37	0.44

Table A.23.2: Northeastern Illinois, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.46	1.55	2.13
Mean	1.28	1.49	2.06
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.46	1.55	2.13
Mean	1.28	1.49	2.06
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Ground			
RMS	1.98	1.47	2.47
Mean	1.98	1.46	2.46
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Building Roofs			
RMS	0.80	1.62	1.81
Mean	0.69	1.51	1.72
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.23.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Northeastern Illinois, USA.

Figure A.23.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Northeastern Illinois, USA.

Figure A.23.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Northeastern Illinois, USA.

Figure A.23.4: Signed vertical errors in Northeastern Illinois, USA.

Figure A.23.5: Signed horizontal errors in Northeastern Illinois, USA.

A.24. Longmont, CO, USA

The reference product at this site is a point cloud generated by terrestrial lidar; see [section 2.3](#) for details.

Table A.24.1: Longmont, CO, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.75	0.64	0.83
Signed Mean	-0.46	0.12	-0.57
Standard dev	0.63	0.67	0.64
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.39	0.33	0.54
Signed Mean	-0.21	-0.09	-0.33
Standard dev	0.35	0.35	0.47
Ground			
RMSE	0.39	0.33	0.54
Signed Mean	-0.21	-0.09	-0.33
Standard dev	0.35	0.35	0.47
Building Corners			
RMSE	1.09	0.93	1.14
Signed Mean	-0.83	0.43	-0.94
Standard dev	0.81	0.96	0.75

Table A.24.2: Longmont, CO, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	0.83	0.99	1.29
Mean	0.68	0.83	1.15
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	0.54	0.51	0.74
Mean	0.50	0.49	0.72
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Ground			
RMS	0.54	0.51	0.74
Mean	0.50	0.49	0.72
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Building Corners			
RMS	1.14	1.44	1.83
Mean	0.94	1.35	1.78
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.24.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Longmont, CO, USA.

Figure A.24.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Longmont, CO, USA.

Figure A.24.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Longmont, CO, USA.

Figure A.24.4: Signed vertical errors in Longmont, CO, USA.

Figure A.24.5: Signed horizontal errors in Longmont, CO, USA.

A.25. Harper’s Ferry, WV, USA

The reference product at this site is a point cloud generated by terrestrial lidar; see [section 2.3](#) for details.

Table A.25.1: Harper’s Ferry, WV, USA ENU error

	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
All Points			
RMSE	0.65	0.53	1.87
Signed Mean	0.09	0.46	−1.76
Standard dev	0.67	0.27	0.66
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMSE	0.23	0.36	1.33
Signed Mean	−0.04	0.31	−1.27
Standard dev	0.24	0.21	0.44
Ground			
RMSE	0.23	0.40	1.18
Signed Mean	−0.09	0.37	−1.14
Standard dev	0.24	0.16	0.34
Building Corners			
RMSE	0.89	0.66	2.28
Signed Mean	0.22	0.62	−2.25
Standard dev	0.95	0.23	0.43
Building Centers			
RMSE	0.39	0.00	0.00
Signed Mean	0.39	0.00	0.00
Standard dev	1.17	0.00	0.00

Table A.25.2: Harper's Ferry, WV, USA error statistics

	Vertical (m)	Horizontal Radial (m)	3D Radial (m)
All Points			
RMS	1.87	0.84	2.05
Mean	1.76	0.72	1.93
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
All Points Except Building Corners			
RMS	1.33	0.43	1.40
Mean	1.27	0.40	1.35
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Ground			
RMS	1.18	0.46	1.27
Mean	1.14	0.44	1.24
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-
Building Corners			
RMS	2.28	1.11	2.54
Mean	2.25	1.03	2.51
LE90, CE90, SE90 Best Est	-	-	-
LE90, CE90, SE90 LUB	-	-	-

Figure A.25.1: Linear vertical errors of measurements in Harper's Ferry, WV, USA.

Figure A.25.2: Radial horizontal errors of measurements in Harper's Ferry, WV, USA.

Figure A.25.3: 3D radial errors of measurements in Harper's Ferry, WV, USA.

Figure A.25.4: Signed vertical errors in Harper's Ferry, WV, USA.

Figure A.25.5: Signed horizontal errors in Harper's Ferry, WV, USA.